

**ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ
ОЛИЙ ТАЪЛИМ, ФАН ВА ИННОВАЦИЯЛАР ВАЗИРЛИГИ**

ТОШКЕНТ ДАВЛАТ ИҚТИСОДИЁТ УНИВЕРСИТЕТИ

**РАҚАМЛИ ИҚТИСОДИЁТНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ
ШАРОИТИДА ИҚТИСОДИЙ ХАВФСИЗЛИКНИ
ТАЪМИНЛАШ МУАММОЛАРИ**

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“Рақамли иқтисодиётни ривожлантириш шароитида иқтисодий хавфсизликни таъминлаш муаммолари” мавзусида халқаро илмий-амалий конференция материаллари туплами. -Т.: ТДИУ, 2023. - 500 б.

Ушбу тупламда миллий иқтисодиётни барқарор ривожлантириш ва юкори иқтисодий усиш суръатларини таъминлашнинг устувор йуналишлари, ялпи ички махсулотда саноат улушини оширишга каратилган ислохотлар ва саноат сиёсатини янада такомиллаштириш чора-тадбирлари, “яшил” иқтисодиёт шароитида мамлакат ижтимоий-иқтисодий тараққиётига эришишда истикболли саноат корхоналарини ривожлантириш йуллари, рақамли иқтисодиёт шароитида мавжуд саноат ишлаб чиқаришни рақамли трансформация қилиш жараёнларини жадаллаштириш орқали ишлаб чиқариш саноатини “драйвер” соҳага айлантириш истикболлари ҳамда барқарор иқтисодий усишни таъминлашнинг турли йуналишларига бағишланган илмий тадқиқот материаллари келтирилган.

Тупламга олий укув юртларида иқтисодий муаммолар буйича илмий изланишлар олиб бораётган профессор-укитувчилар, докторантлар, тадқиқотчилар, вазирлик, кумита ва турли мулкчилик шаклидаги корхона ва ташкилотларнинг етакчи мутахассислари, магистрлар ва иқтидорли талабаларнинг илмий изланишлари натижалари киритилган.

Тупламда келтирилган материалларнинг мазмуни, ундаги статистик маълумотлар ва келтирилган ҳуқуқий-меъёрий ҳужжатларнинг ҳаққонийлиги, танқидий фикр-мулоҳазалар ва таклифларга муаллифларнинг узлари масъулдирлар.

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Нейромаркетинг ривожини учинчи сабаби бу нейрофанлардаги ривож, айнан асаб жараёнларини усули ва технологиясини янгиликлари, улардан нафақат клиник изланишларда балки ижтимоий масалаларнинг ечими мавжудлигидадир. Ижтимоий иқтисодий ҳаракат асослари, қарор қабул қилиш, савдо алоқалари ривожини ва бошфаларнинг бари абстракт тушунча бўлиб инсон миясида вужудга келади. Индивид миясидаги асаб жараёнларини ўрганиш бозор алмашинуви натижалари учун танлов, сабаб, қарор қабул қилиш жараёнини ўрганиш орқали амалга оширилади.

Мия ривожининг назорати 21 асрда кенг тарқалиб ижтимоий ва гуманитар фанларда, яъни:нейроиктисод, нейросоциология, нейросиёсат, нейроменеджмент ва нейромаркетинг фанларида ривожини топди. Изланишларнинг янги назарий моделлари, методларга талаб бир тарафлама бўлса, иккинчи тарафдан мия фаолиятини ўрганиш нейромаркетингни мустақил ривожига, нейромаркетинг концепциясини мустақил йўналиш сифатида ривожланишига омил бўлди.

Адабиётлар:

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EXAMINING THE EFFECTS AT THE INTERFACE OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY AND THE LABOR MARKET

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Annotation: The application of labor relations and the growing integration of digital technology into labor market processes are the main topics of this research. The aim of this study is to evaluate the increasing utilization of information technology in the workplace and investigate its consequences. The importance of this study stems from the requirement for legislative measures to tackle the creation of novel labor relations models brought about by the integration of digital and information technologies. This involves the quick growth of alternative job models including freelance work, telecommuting, and self-employment, as well as the conversion of important labor market activities to electronic formats

Keywords: labor relations, job market, employment, digital economy, information technology.

Ключевые слова: трудовые отношения, рынок труда, занятость, цифровая экономика, информационные технологии.

Rapid advancements in the new industrial and technology revolution will significantly alter the employment market and the fundamentals of national economies, resulting in profound changes.

Breakthrough discoveries, new concepts, and digital technologies are critical in reshaping labor markets and impacting many aspects of social and labor relations as global resources and opportunities are redistributed.

Digital technologies stand out among all the changes because they are developing at a rapid pace, permeating every element of life and industry, and radically changing the nature of worker relations and the labor market.

Although the term "digital economy" first appeared in scholarly literature in 1995, it is especially relevant to consider how digitization has affected the labor market in the present day. This is due to the fact that the pace and scope of technological development during the shift to the fourth industrial revolution are very different from those of the first three.

One significant contemporary development that directly affects labor relations dynamics is digitalization, which brings more flexibility and similarities to civil law relations. Additionally, it affects employment both nationally and regionally. The labor market and labor relations are unavoidably impacted by the transformation from an industrial to a post-industrial society, sometimes known as the "digital economy" or the move from Economy 3.0 to Economy 4.0. Within the multidisciplinary subject of economics and law, there has been a rising emphasis over the last five years on investigating how labor relations are affected by digitization.

Prominent academics who have studied this subject include R. Berger, J. Valenduk, P. Ven-dramin, V.B. Gould, M. Graham, G. Johnson, I. Dosen, K. Land-Kazlauskas, N.L. Lyutov, V. de Stefano, and others. In particular, scholars have begun to focus particularly on the rise of novel and nontraditional job roles connected to computer and mobile device usage [2].

It is imperative for employers to use a diverse range of digital technologies in order to gain a competitive advantage or maintain their current market positions. These technologies power the continuous process of digital transformation and include neurotechnology, artificial intelligence, quantum technologies, blockchain (distributed ledger systems), robotics, sensorics, wireless communication, virtual and augmented reality, and the industrial internet.

According to N. I. Tatarinova: "Under the effectiveness of people's labor, - we understand - such use of it, in which the efficiency of social production increases, the population increases, the harmonious development of women's personality and its actual equality with men is achieved."

H. I. Kungurova introduces the concept of "the effect of women's employment", dividing it into the economic effect, that is, the effect of a woman's performance of the production function, and the social effect - brought by the family and domestic function of a woman. "The effectiveness of women's employment depends not only on the economic effect, but also on the social effect, which consists in the continuous and comprehensive development of women and their successful fulfillment of the functions of giving birth and bringing up new generations."

Issues concerning the mechanism of functioning of the social protection system were raised by foreign scientists-economists S. Golinovskaya, M. Zhukovsky, R. Palacios, G. Spencer, M. J. Fischer, and in the scientific works of Hengstendberg. The stages of formation and development of the system of social protection of the population during the pandemic in the CIS countries

and some issues of formation of social protection of the population, theoretical and methodological foundations, models of social protection of the population and features of their realization were studied by I. Andreeva, D.J. Bichkov, E.E. Grishina, T.M.Maleva, E.A.Tsatsura, O.A. Feoktistova and other scientists-economists.

Scientists-economists of our country A.V.Vakhobov, G.X.Abdurakhmanov, H.P.Abulkasimov, P.Z.Hashimov and scientific works of Abdullaeva are devoted to the coverage of theoretical and conceptual foundations of the economy of the social sphere and social protection system. Some issues of financing the social sphere, living standards of the population, mechanisms, methods and support of the population were described in the research works of M.A.Hakimova, M.X. Ganiev, B.B.Bakhtiyarov.

The methods of system analysis, historicism and logic, induction and deduction, comparative and sample study, econometric analysis and forecasting were used in the research process.

Unquestionably, the transition from an industrial to a digital economy modifies both the volume and kind of work interactions. The broad use of digital technology has led to several important areas of transformation that have a big impact on labor and employment. The following can be used to identify these areas:

- The term automation describes the process of replacing human work with machine labor.
- Converting tangible items and papers into digital ones and vice versa is known as digitalization.
- Digital platforms operate as middlemen in the algorithmic structuring of financial transactions.

The COVID-19 epidemic has brought attention to the growing trend of digital labor platforms around the world. Nonetheless, there is a chance that these workers' employers would deteriorate their working circumstances due to the absence of prompt legal regulation for new types of employment. Furthermore, there are ramifications for the general rise in employment prospects from the increasing use of digital technology in contemporary industry [3].

First off, there is an increase in jobs within the information and communication technology industry. 8.2 million people worked in this industry in the member states of the European Union in 2016, making up 3.7% of all jobs at that time. The number of experts working in the sector of information and communication technology has consistently increased over time, as has its share of overall employment, thanks to the growth of digitalization.

Second, new job possibilities are being created by digitization in a number of economic areas, most notably the services sector. In many nations, the need for labor has increased in sectors like culture, recreation, building,

healthcare, energy, and agriculture, while it has decreased in sectors like manufacturing, business services, commerce, and transportation. Simultaneously, there has been a significant increase in the quantity of individuals working in online platform-based occupations related to lodging, transportation, and other service industries. These positions frequently include part-time, temporary, and flexible work schedules.

Going forward, it is anticipated that the trend of obfuscating distinctions between various operations, enhancing operational flexibility, globalization, and openness in stakeholder interactions would persist. Employers will always need workers, but full-time jobs and conventional work arrangements will probably become less common.

The employment market's structure is already being impacted by the digitization process. Openness and transparency are being embraced by organizations in their dealings with suppliers, clients, inspectors, and managers. Online platforms are helping firms become more flexible and adaptable to the ever-changing economic situation. Cooperation is essential in the digital economy, both inside and outside of businesses. Online platforms have grown significantly in the last several years, especially in the travel and lodging industries. The capacity to efficiently monetize dispersed private assets with the aid of digital technology is what is fueling this expansion. Furthermore, the sharing economy has contributed to the growth of online marketplaces as consumers choose to "share" things rather than make direct purchases.

The emergence of internet platforms has made it possible for highly skilled persons with extraordinary potential to work on many projects concurrently in remote or virtual environments, transcending geographical limitations. This occasionally entails actions that cross national borders, calling for more international cooperation, coordination, and harmonization of many aspects of national legal systems. Additionally, new prospects for self-employment are brought about by digital technology. People may work from anywhere, even at home or at a coffee shop, thanks to online platforms that allow for flexibility in the workplace. Furthermore, women, individuals with impairments, and those living in distant places now have more opportunities to participate in the production process because to technological improvements.

A large number of platform users work part-time jobs or are employed part-time. According to studies, independent contractors use platforms to establish their own businesses 25%, augment their regular income 25%, fill temporary jobs such those in construction 20%, and more. About 80% of the work done on platforms is done on-demand, meaning clients get in touch with contractors directly when they need certain tasks completed. Global connection and real-time mobile device usage have made work more virtual and accessible at any time and from any location. Because of this, businesses

must continue to run successful digital business operations and manage a dynamic talent ecosystem even in situations where their personnel are distributed across many time zones and geographic regions. Robotics, self-driving cars, sensors, AI, and the Internet of Things are all rapidly changing the nature of work and encouraging more flexibility and the use of temporary workers to quickly adjust to changing business procedures.

The growing disparity between significant job losses in industries like catering, the arts, culture, retail, and construction and the expansion of employment opportunities in high-skilled service sectors like information, communications, finance, insurance, and delivery is a noteworthy trend in the global labor market that was especially noticeable during the pandemic years 2020– 2021. It is predicted that the automation of several facets of human activity would result in the automation of more than half of all labor functions by 2025. Furthermore, it is predicted that up to 50% of labor processes globally would be automated in the next ten years, rendering many occupations obsolete. Simultaneously, new positions requiring vastly different skill sets will appear, requiring sophisticated training and staff retraining.

Employers and employees' interactions as well as the labor market's quantitative features are altered by the digitization of the economy. The emergence and spread of remote work arrangements, which promote labor decentralization with respect to time and place, is one notable shift. This puts the conventional employment paradigm to the test and creates a flexible, virtual labor market. Another effect is that it becomes harder for people to plan their long-term career routes since a particular expertise is no longer a guarantee of long-term employment, rather, market demand becomes the deciding factor. As a result, there is a growing need for employees to have attributes including the flexibility to adjust to changing conditions, continued participation in the labor market, and continuous knowledge of their marketability.

The emergence of digitization and the growth of the on-demand economy have liberated employment from geographical and temporal restrictions. Individual autonomy reduces employer control over work progress, increases individual freedom, and provides an easy way to track attendance, electronic badge systems are widely used in big and medium-sized organizations worldwide to record working hours. Moreover, businesses can track employee activity by implementing webcam monitoring. However, there are issues that may jeopardize employees' rights, welfare, and psychological comfort at work. It's unclear, for example, how much an employer may snoop into workers' personal life, what rules apply to vacation time, and whether workers can refuse to answer calls, emails, or SMS messages after hours.

One other difficulty in setting up remote work is using a sophisticated electronic digital signature in the interaction between the employer and the distant employee. The question here is whether the employer should pay for

the signature or should both parties bear the expense. It also concerns the necessity of using the signature on all orders, instructions, job and work guidelines, regulations, and other local legal documents that the employer gives to the remote worker.

Recording disciplinary infractions is another major challenge. Digital technology, such as the remote worker's failure to contact the employer online at the appointed time, alert the employer to these infractions.

It might be challenging to establish in court whether the employee's actions or technological problems, such as a malfunctioning Skype application or a poor internet signal, caused the failure. There could be other difficulties, such as precisely documenting downtime brought on by hardware or software malfunctions, virus outbreaks, or staff error, among other things.

The digital economy places great importance on collective bargaining and employee consultation between businesses and employees. The impact of digitalization on collective labor rights has been the subject of preliminary comparative research by the International Labour Organization (ILO), especially when it comes to online platforms. However, there haven't yet been any globally recognized solutions that meet the needs of several different nations. National practices show that workers may migrate to new digital technologies more smoothly and with less disruption if they are informed and advised beforehand.

The collective ties between employers and their associations and employees' trade unions and their associations across a range of employment arrangements, including both classic and non-traditional forms, are impacted by the digitization of work. The way social partners interact is radically changed by computer and digital technology, causing a transition that affects all sectors of the economy.

After the pandemic's effects on the Uzbekistan economy in March 2020, there has been a notable rise in the use of remote work and the development of digital labor platforms inside the digital economy. The emergence of these platforms, serving as middlemen between employers and workers, has fundamentally altered the landscape of labor and social connections. More laws and regulations have therefore been required to deal with this change. The emergence of these platforms has given marginalized groups, such as young people, migrant workers, women with children, and those with disabilities, who face discrimination in the traditional job market more opportunities to find employment. As a result, governmental information systems have been created with the intention of giving these groups options.

The labor market is changing due to the economy's digitization, which makes it necessary to embrace new tools, especially digital ones, to improve the quality of regulations. It also needs a sufficient legal structure. The rise of new professions necessitates modifying the qualifications of employees, increases the need for new competences and abilities, and promotes the

expansion of online and remote learning. The drawbacks of the labor market's rapid digitalization include the possibility of employer exploitation with regard to working conditions, treatment, and compensation, a growing skills gap between employers and employees, and an increased risk of unemployment.

There are drawbacks to the job market's digitization as well. Many employees struggle to quickly gain the skills required for developing professions due to the unequal pace of digital growth across various industries. Furthermore, companies could not always implement contemporary digital technology quickly, which might lead to disparities in the labor market and a higher risk of unemployment. In order to effectively address these particular and intricate concerns, state legislation must be implemented in a methodical manner, and digital technologies that enable the identification, analysis, and proactive mitigation of potential negative impacts must be established.

A key component of the Industry 4.0 paradigm, digitalization involves the creation of a digital economy and permeates every facet of society, including individual and collective work interactions. Similar to the labor market, these relationships are immediately impacted by digitization and necessitate extensive adjustment in terms of theoretical models, fundamental traits, and modern regulatory requirements.

Divergent views exist throughout the scientific community about how digitization affects unemployment rates. According to the author, while digitalization processes may short-term exacerbate structural unemployment, they will inevitably drive workforce training systems to change in order to accommodate new professions over the long and medium terms.

Relationships between employers and employees are changing dramatically, and remote and flexible work arrangements are becoming more and more common. In addition, the importance of intellectual labor is growing relative to conventional physical labor. Ensuring that workers have appropriate social protection measures in place and limiting their vulnerability are the main concerns connected with working remotely. This entails maintaining safety requirements, work laws, and equitable job opportunities. Instead of being in the best interests of the workers, non-traditional types of employment sometimes arise out of need. This raises questions about how humanization and digitization can coexist and runs counter to the objective of fostering more compassionate social and professional connections. Collaboration amongst all parties involved in social and labor connections is crucial to resolving this paradox.

"Cloud work," as opposed to traditional employment and current remote work practices, is predicted to be one of the main kinds of employment in the near future.

The fast advancement of digitalization in the economy results in the substitution of specific financial resources with novel ones, the birth of

inventive resource management tools, and a rise in the variety of interactions between members of an organization. Simultaneously, businesses are moving away from inflexible industry-focused structures and toward more integrated, service-oriented models. Consequently, advancements in technology bring about a profound transformation of the labor field, altering the actors, content, type, composition, and scope of human labor. In order to handle changing connections and new dynamics, new standards and laws are also required.

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